

Culture-Competent Machine Learning in Social Robotics

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Abstract—Nowadays, Machine Learning (ML) is largely applied to Intelligent Machines, empowering automatization. Thanks to ML, researchers were able to give birth to the field of Social Robotics (SR), namely the field of Robotics which designs robots capable of interacting socially with humans. Among the SR’s objectives, researchers try to embed cultural competence in robots. Since, in order to design culture-competent robots, it is also necessary to design culturally competent ML algorithms, this paper proposes a metric for measuring cultural competence inside ML algorithms and a mitigation strategy for embedding this property inside classical ML algorithms. The metric and the mitigation strategy are evaluated on an SR use case, which dataset has been *ad hoc* collected.

Index Terms—Culture-competent Machine Learning, Social Robotics, Image Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Robotics perception and interaction design have largely benefited from the development of Machine Learning (ML) [14], which has now achieved super-human performance in many fields [9]. The faith in new technologies, such as ML, pushed researchers to investigate how to enhance robots’ social and cultural skills, giving birth to the field of Social Robotics (SR) [11]. Among SR objectives, researchers aim to embed cultural competence in social robots, due to the role culture plays in human-robot interaction¹. To do so, it is necessary to develop culturally competent ML algorithms, namely the ability of ML algorithms to adapt their behavior to the cultural contexts and to react appropriately. Generally, SR researchers have investigated the impact of culture on the perception of robots from humans [5]. In the literature, attempts exist regarding the design of culturally competent Artificial Intelligence (AI) [8]. These attempts mostly lie in the model-based approaches [8], while ML has slightly touched on this problem [4], [6]. These works did not consider two issues when they realized their architectures: it is not always permitted to easily preprocess data and current datasets do not equally represent every culture [17]. In this paper, we propose to create a metric for measuring the cultural (in)competence of ML models and a mitigation strategy that comes from Multitask Learning [19], tested using a Convolutional Neural Network named ResNet50 [10]. The metric and the mitigation strategy are evaluated on an SR test case, which dataset has been *ad hoc* collected. The rest of the paper is organized

as follows. Section II presents the problem definition and our mitigation approach for a culturally incompetent ML algorithm. Section III shows the results of a standard ML algorithm applied to the SR test case and the difference between it and our proposal. Section IV concludes the paper.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Culturally Competent ML

The proposed mitigation strategy is theoretically grounded and comes from Multi-Task learning [19]. In our culturally competent ML framework, the dataset embeds cultural information: $\mathcal{D}_n = \{(X_1, C_1, Y_1), \dots, (X_n, C_n, Y_n)\}$, where $C \in \mathcal{C}$ labels the culture of each sample, X_i represents the input, and Y_i the corresponding output of each sample. Given the fact that \mathcal{D}_n may be not balanced with respect to the cultures [17], a culturally incompetent ML model may minimize the overall error ERR, but there could be still a high error on samples that come from minority cultures [7]. In order to simulate this fact, the dataset is divided such that, during the learning and validation phases, the learning and validation sets are formed by 80% of samples coming from a majority culture and 20% of the rest ones. In a culturally competent ML scenario, the model function should be a good estimator for $\mathbb{P}\{Y|X, C\}$, $\forall C \in \mathcal{C}$. This implies that the error in each culture called ERR^C , must be taken into account to evaluate the cultural competence of a model, together with the overall error ERR. We will then define cultural (in)competence (CIC) as follows

$$CIC = \hat{\mathbb{E}}_C \left| ERR^C - \min_{C' \in \mathcal{C}} ERR^{C'} \right|, \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\mathbb{E}}_C = 1/|\mathcal{C}| \sum_{C \in \mathcal{C}}$. The goal of embedding cultural competence in ML is to minimize both the overall error ERR and CIC.

For what concerns the framework, the mitigation strategy can be applied both to Shallow and Deep Learning models. In this paper, we have analyzed the effect of the architecture on Deep Learning (DL) models. Usually, in DL, a convolutional neural network, such as ResNet50 [10], would have one output for a binary classification problem, and one loss function l would be the cost applied to that single output for each sample.

¹<https://www.springer.com/journal/12369>

In our proposed solution, there are as many outputs as many cultures, and for each output, the loss l function becomes:

$$l = \begin{cases} 0 & C \neq O_i \\ cost + \gamma * \left\| \mathbf{w}_C - \sum_{C' \in \mathcal{C}} \mathbf{w}_{C'} \right\|_2^2 & C = O_i \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where O_i is the i^{th} output related to one specific culture, the cost is the one applied for the general problem (e.g. Binary Cross-Entropy in binary classification problems), γ is the hyperparameter of the regularizer. The mitigation strategy can be applied also to other algorithms, but in this specific paper we present results that compare this algorithm using the classical ML approach and with our mitigation strategy.

B. SR Case of Study

Social Robotics applications encompass health and social care [13], tourism [12] and education [3]. Among these applications, SR researchers focused on home assistance for elderly people, despite not developing culturally competent architectures [1]. During a home assistance scenario, robots must navigate in an indoor environment and exploit information to perform tasks, such as monitoring people’s health and keeping company [16]. In this scenario, for example, a social robot must be able to know if lamps are on or off because they are strong indicators of someone awakening at night that may need some help. This is conceptualized in ML as a binary image classification problem. Since lamps are different based on where they are, they have cultural information. In our dataset, we have collected images from three different cultures: Chinese, French, and Turkish.

III. EXPERIMENTS

All the models have been trained using Model Selection and Transfer Learning. Model Selection refers to the fact that the algorithm used to learn the model have a set of hyperparameters [2]. The technique consists of splitting the data in order to select the best hyperparameters, searched in a grid [15]. Transfer Learning [18] refers to using a representation learned from similar problems and adapting this representation to the actual problem. DL models are data greedy and with a small dataset, it is easy to overfit the model. In this case, we have used the weights of the net learned using ImageNet² dataset, and then we have frozen all the layers except the last one. Tab. I shows the results obtained using standard ResNet50 model.

Majority	ERR ^{Chinese}	ERR ^{French}	ERR ^{Turkish}	CIC
Chinese	11.2%±4.4%	16.9%±5.2%	23.3%±3.4%	6.0%±1.2%
French	18.8%±7.1%	11.6%±6.8%	26.1%±5.1%	7.2%±1.8%
Turkish	20.2%±4.7%	22.6%±6.7%	13.1%±3.2%	5.5%±2.6%

TABLE I: **Standard ResNet50**

Tab. II shows the results obtained using mitigated ResNet50 model, where the optimal lambda selected is the one with minimum ERR.

²<https://www.image-net.org/>

Majority	ERR ^{Chinese}	ERR ^{French}	ERR ^{Turkish}	CIC
Chinese	10.6%±2.3%	13.8%±2.0%	19.3%±3.2%	4.1%±1.8%
French	15.9%±3.5%	9.4%±1.9%	21.5%±2.7%	6.2%±1.6%
Turkish	17.2%±2.8%	18.0%±3.0%	10.6%±1.4%	4.7%±1.9%

TABLE II: **Mitigated ResNet50**

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Using effective standard ML algorithms is not sufficient for embedding cultural competence. This incompetence is measurable and can be evaluated using the proposed CIC. Our mitigation strategy enhances the cultural competence of the model while preserving or empowering model performance.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Abdi, A. Al-Hindawi, T. Ng, and M. P. Vizcaychipi. Scoping review on the use of socially assistive robot technology in elderly care. *BMJ Open*, 8(2):e018815, 2018.
- [2] C. C. Aggarwal. *Neural networks and deep learning*. Springer, 2023.
- [3] M. Alemi, A. Meghdari, and M. Ghazisaedy. Employing humanoid robots for teaching english language in iranian junior high-schools. *International Journal of Humanoid Robotics*, 11(03):1450022, 2014.
- [4] M. Bautin, L. Vijayarenu, and S. Skiena. International sentiment analysis for news and blogs. In *International Conference on Weblogs and Social Media*, 2008.
- [5] B. Bruno, N. Chong, H. Kamide, S. Kanoria, and Others. Paving the way for culturally competent robots: a position paper. In *IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication*, 2017.
- [6] R. Chen and P. L. Rau. Deep learning model for humor recognition of different cultures. In *International Conference on Cross-Cultural Design. Experience and Product Design Across Cultures*, 2021.
- [7] N. Cristianini. *The Shortcut: Why Intelligent Machines Do Not Think Like Us*. CRC Press, 2023.
- [8] C. Faucher and F. C. Ditzinger. *Advances in culturally-aware intelligent systems and in cross-cultural psychological studies*. Springer, 2018.
- [9] K. Grace, J. Salvatier, A. Dafoe, B. Zhang, and O. Evans. When will ai exceed human performance? evidence from ai experts. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 62:729–754, 2018.
- [10] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2016.
- [11] F. Hegel, C. Muhl, B. Wrede, M. Hielscher-Fastabend, and Others. Understanding social robots. In *International Conferences on Advances in Computer-Human Interactions*, 2009.
- [12] S. Ivanov, U. Gretzel, K. Berezina, M. Sigala, and Others. Progress on robotics in hospitality and tourism: a review of the literature. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Technology*, 10(4):489–521, 2019.
- [13] D. L. Johanson, H. S. Ahn, and E. Broadbent. Improving interactions with healthcare robots: A review of communication behaviours in social and healthcare contexts. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, 13(8):1835–1850, 2021.
- [14] A. I. Károly, P. Galambos, J. Kuti, and I. J. Rudas. Deep learning in robotics: Survey on model structures and training strategies. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, 51(1):266–279, 2021.
- [15] L. Oneto. *Model Selection and Error Estimation in a Nutshell*. Springer, 2020.
- [16] I. Pedersen, S. Reid, and K. Aspevig. Developing social robots for aging populations: A literature review of recent academic sources. *Sociology Compass*, 12:e12585, 2018.
- [17] S. Shankar, Y. Halpern, E. Breck, J. Atwood, and Others. No classification without representation: Assessing geodiversity issues in open data sets for the developing world. In *Neural Information Processing Systems*, 2017.
- [18] K. Weiss, T. M. Khoshgoftaar, and D. Wang. A survey of transfer learning. *Journal of Big Data*, 3:9, 2016.
- [19] Y. Zhang and Q. Yang. An overview of multi-task learning. *National Science Review*, 5(1):30–43, 2018.